

Synthesis of some Thiooxalatometallates (M = Ge, Sn and W)

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The preparations of thiooxalatometallates of germanium(IV), tin(IV) and tungsten(VI), viz. $(\text{guH})_4[\text{GeS}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{M}_2[\text{SnS}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where M = K, guH, QuH, 1,10-phenH, pyH), $\text{Na}_2[\text{SnOS}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)] \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{BH})_2[\text{WO}_2\text{S}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ (where B = 1/2 en and gu) are described. The ir spectra and TG results of the compounds are discussed.

Literature survey shows that although oxalatometallates and thiometallates are known for many metals but except a potassium compound¹, $\text{K}_2[\text{SnS}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which was also not studied by TG and ir spectroscopy, no other thiooxalatometallates has been reported. The present communication describes a simpler method for the preparation of the above mentioned compound and the isolation and studies on several other hitherto unknown thiooxalatometallates of germanium(IV), tin(IV) and tungsten(VI).

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of the compounds are given in Table 1. The thiooxalato compounds of Ge^{IV} and Sn^{IV} are mostly water-soluble, whilst the tungsten compounds of ethylenediaminium and guanidinium are insoluble. Their solubility characteristics and colour indicated them to be free from corresponding insoluble sulphides. Potassium thiooxalato-stannate was reported in the literature as a dihydrate, but higher hydration was observed through the present work. Its aqueous solutions showed much higher conductance values than those for solutions of potassium sulphate of equivalent concentrations, which suggested its appreciable hydrolysis¹ at room temperature.

TG studies : The TG curve of guanidinium oxalato-germanate indicated its decomposition from 30° and at 300° GeO_2 was obtained. The TG

curves of quinolinium, *o*-phenanthroline and pyridinium thiooxalato-stannates showed the compounds to decompose from 50° and formed corresponding anhydrous compounds as unstable intermediates at 230, 190 and 140° respectively. Tin dioxide was obtained from them as residue at 330, 450 and 190° respectively. Potassium compounds $\text{K}_2[\text{SnS}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, decomposed from 40°. The compound did not yield any stable intermediate at higher temperature. The percent weight-loss at 400° and the chemical analysis of the residue suggested it to consist of $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, SnO_2 and $\text{K}_2[\text{SnO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$. Sodium oxothiooxalato compound, $\text{Na}_2[\text{SnOS}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)] \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ decomposed from 40° and formed probably a mixture of $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and SnO_2 at 290° as suggested from the loss in weight observed in the TG curve.

The thermogram of $\text{enH}_2[\text{WO}_2\text{S}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ indicated its decomposition from 40° and the formation of $\text{enH}_2[\text{WO}_3(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ as stable intermediate was observed in the region 80–100°. The observation was corroborated by chemical analysis of the product. WO_3 resulted from it at 480°. The guanidinium compound, $(\text{guH})_2[\text{WO}_2\text{S}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ decomposed from 130° and the formation of $(\text{guH})_2[\text{WO}_3(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ as intermediate was observed at 160–210°. The chemical analysis of the product supported the above observation. Further decomposition to WO_3 was observed at 360°. The above TG data of the thiooxalatometallates support the

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR THIOOXALATOMETALLATES (M = Ge^{IV}, Sn^{IV} AND W^{VI})

Compd ^a	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	N/Na/K	Ge/Sn/W	S	C ₂ O ₄
(guH) ₄ [GeS ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₂].10H ₂ O	22.80 (22.93)	9.98 (9.91)	9.10 (8.73)	23.64 (24.02)
K ₂ [SnS(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].12H ₂ O	13.0 (12.56)	19.09 (19.12)	5.25 (5.15)	27.52 (28.35)
Na ₂ [SnOS(C ₂ O ₄)] 7H ₂ O	10.89 (10.78)	27.8 (27.81)	7.26 (7.49)	20.6 (20.62)
(guH) ₂ [SnS(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].H ₂ O	18.07 (18.06)	25.18 (25.53)	6.96 (6.88)	37.67 (37.86)
(quH) ₂ [SnS(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].H ₂ O	4.68 (4.63)	19.9 (19.65)	5.29 (5.29)	29.57 (29.13)
(1,10-phenH) ₂ [SnS(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].6H ₂ O	6.95 (7.02)	14.88 (14.89)	3.74 (4.01)	22.16 (22.07)
(pyH) ₂ [SnS(C ₂ O ₄) ₂].H ₂ O	5.54 (5.54)	24.06 (23.51)	6.22 (6.34)	35.63 (35.63)
(enH ₂)[WO ₂ S(C ₂ O ₄)]	6.93 (7.04)	47.34 (46.23)	8.23 (8.04)	21.11 (22.12)
(guH) ₂ [WO ₂ S(C ₂ O ₄)]	18.14 (18.43)	39.74 (40.33)	7.35 (7.02)	19.49 (19.31)

^agu = guanidine; qu = quinoline; py = pyridine; en = ethylenediamine; 1,10-phen = 1,10-phenanthroline.

general observation that in air at higher temperature M–S bond gets easily converted to stronger M–O bond.

Ir studies : The thiooxalatogermanates, thiooxalatostannates and thiooxalatotungstates showed ir spectral bands at 470–530 and 765–810 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of chelating oxalate group² in them. Other diagnostic bands for chelating oxalate group were observed at 1520–1660 and at 1330–1400 cm⁻¹, but these might also be due to δ_{H–O–H}, δ_{NH₃} and ν_{NH} respectively in the case of hydrated and cationic organic amine compounds studied. The latter compounds showed bands also at 3000–3500 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} mode of lattice water or ν_{NH}, whilst overlapping of these bands was quite probable. A strong band³ observed at 795–810 cm⁻¹ in the thiooxalatogermanates and thiooxalatostannates was due to bands for chelated oxalate group and ν_{Ge–O} or ν_{Sn–O}. Guanidinium thiooxalatogermanate showed another band at 640 cm⁻¹ due to Ge–O stretching. The bands observed at 800 and 870 cm⁻¹ in the case of dioxothiooxalatotungstates were due to ν_{W–O}, but the former band merged with the one for chelated oxalate group. The oxalatothiotungstates showed bands at 460 and 480 cm⁻¹ due to W–S stretching⁴, but overlapping

of these bands with the chelating oxalate group in this region probably occurred. A comparison of ir spectra of GeS₂ and guanidinium thiooxalatogermanate suggested that the band for the latter at 275 cm⁻¹ was due to Ge–S stretching. The thiooxalatostannates showed sharp band at 330–335 and 370–385 cm⁻¹ which were probably due to Sn–S stretching as found with SnS₂.

Experimental

B.D.H. and E. Merck chemicals were used. Ge, Sn and W were estimated gravimetrically as their oxides. Alkali metals were determined gravimetrically as their sulphates after necessary separation from other metals. Nitrogen was determined by semimicro Dumas method. Oxalate was determined permanganometrically after precipitating calcium oxalate from a solution of a compound from which sulphide was driven off beforehand by digesting with hydrochloric acid. Sulphur in the compounds was determined as BaSO₄ after treating them with bromine water.

TG was done as reported earlier⁵ by heating the compounds at the rate of 2°/min upto 400°. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer.

Guanidinium thiooxalatogermanate hydrate, (guH)₄[GeS₂(C₂O₄)₂].10H₂O : Freshly precipitated germanium sulphide prepared from germanium (1 g), was dissolved in a solution of guanidinium carbonate (3 g). Oxalic acid (1.2 g) was added to it to bring down pH of the solution to 5–6. The mixture was concentrated in a vacuum desiccator and alcohol was then added. The resulting crystals were dried over fused CaCl₂. The compound (2 g) was found highly hygroscopic.

Potassium thiooxalatostannate hydrate, K₂[SnS(C₂O₄)₂].12H₂O : To a solution (60 mg) of potassium heptaoxalatodistannate (3 g), excess oxalic acid (Sn : C₂O₄ = 1 : 10) was added, warmed and H₂S passed through it till saturation. Alcohol was then added to the solution and the resulting fine crystals were washed with alcohol and dried in air (2 g).

Sodium oxothiooxalatostannate hydrate, Na₂[SnOS(C₂O₄)].7H₂O : A solution (50 ml) of Na₂[Sn(OH)₆] (2 g) and oxalic acid (6 g) was warmed and saturated with H₂S. On adding alcohol crystals appeared which was dried as above (3 g).

(BH)₂[SnS(C₂O₄)₂].xH₂O, where B = pyridine, guanidine, quinoline and 1,10-phenanthroline.
General method : A solution (50 ml) of SnCl₄.5H₂O (2 g) and oxalic acid (8 g) was warmed and saturated with H₂S. A mixture (10 ml) of guanidinium carbonate (1 g) or other base (1.5–2 g) and oxalic acid (2 g) was also saturated with H₂S and then added dropwise to the previous mixture with stirring. Quinolinium and orthophenanthroline compounds were precipitated during mixing, whilst pyridinium compound was obtained through addition of alcohol to the resultant solution. The guanidinium compound was obtained on evaporation of the solution in a vacuum desiccator. The crystals were filtered and dried in air.

Ethylenediaminium dioxothiooxalatotungstate, en-H₂[WO₂S(C₂O₄)] (en = ethylenediamine) : Freshly precipitated tungsten(VI) trioxide hydrate was dissolved in ethylenediamine (40%) till satura-

tion. It was filtered and H₂S passed through the solution for ~0.5 h when reddish-yellow crystals of (en-H₂)[WS₄] separated out. The crystals were washed successively with water and alcohol, and dried. To a saturated solution of the thiotungstate, an oxalic acid solution was added in the ratio thiotungstate : oxalic acid = 1 : 1. Air was then passed through the bright yellow mixture (pH~3) for ~ 8 h till no smell of H₂S was perceived from the dull yellow resultant solution (pH~6). On adding alcohol to it a light yellow precipitate was obtained, which was washed with alcohol and dried over fused CaCl₂.

Guanidinium dioxothiooxalatotungstate, (guH₂)-[WO₂S(C₂O₄)] (gu = guanidine) : An aqueous solution (40%) of guanidine carbonate was saturated with freshly precipitated tungsten trioxide hydrate. It was filtered and H₂S passed till it assumed reddish-yellow colour. On adding a solution of oxalic acid to it in the ratio W⁶⁺ : C₂O₄²⁻ = 1 : 1, light yellow precipitate appeared, which was dried as above.

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